

D1.1 – Project Handbook

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Summary sheet

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0.9	31/7/2023	VUB	Draft for partners review
1.0	25/08/2023	VUB	Final version with feedback from partners incorporated

ACRONYMS

CT5: Cooperation tool

PC: Project Coordinator

SC: Steering Committee

GA: General Assembly

AB: Advisory Board

WP: Work package

D&C: Dissemination and Communication

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1.Executive summary

Deliverable 1.1 (Project Handbook) presents an overview of the procedures agreed by the NEMO Consortium for the seamless implementation of the project as well as of the selected tool for project, financial and internal data management.

This document represents a central resource for project partners, covering (i) the governance framework, (ii) quality assurance procedures, (iii) risk management, (iv) financial management, (v) project management and data management tools, (vi) and initial guidelines for internal and external communication.

2.Partners’ Contributions

Partner institution	Sections	Description of the contribution
VUB	All	Deliverable draft
ICONS	10	Section draft
All partners	All	Review of draft deliverable

3. Introduction

This deliverable has been prepared in the framework of WP1 and is intended to be a collection of core information for the efficient management of the project. It is derived from tasks 1.1 (Scientific coordination and governance) and 1.2 (Administrative project management) and is overarching to all other WPs. For this reason, D1.1 is the result of collaborative work from all project partners, who have reviewed and agreed on the proposed procedures and tools.

D1.1 lays some initial considerations on the use of internal and external repositories to be further detailed in the Data management plan (D1.2) and its planned updates (D1.3 and D1.4). The initial guidelines concerning internal and external communication are to be further developed in the DEC plan (D8.1) and its update (D8.2).

4. Governance

NEMO's governance includes the following bodies to ensure an efficient and effective implementation while maximizing the impact of the project results:

- Project Coordinator
- General Assembly
- Steering Committee
- Advisory Board

An overview of the planned schedule for their recurrent meetings is presented in section 4.5.

4.1. Project Coordinator

The Project Coordinator (PC) is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

The PC leads the scientific coordination of the project with the support of all partners. It also leads the operational management of the project, including the monitoring of the use of resources and constant support to project partners.

4.2. General Assembly

The General Assembly is the main decision-making body of the Consortium and will include representatives of all project partners.

As set in the Consortium Agreement, the General Assembly is Responsible for proposing changes to the Description of the Action, proposal of budget-related changes, modification of the background and listed third parties and entities under the same control identified in the Consortium Agreement, addition or removal of parties to or from the Consortium, and identification and management of breaches, among others.

4.3. Steering Committee

The Steering Committee is the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, reporting to and being accountable to the General Assembly. It includes all WP leaders.

As established in the Consortium Agreement, the Steering Committee has the following responsibilities:

- Execute and implement the decisions of the General Assembly.
- Monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project.
- Assess the progress of the project and its compliance with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the Consortium Plan to the General Assembly
- Support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables.

- Prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Granting Authority in respect of the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 17 and Annex 5 Section “Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility” and of Section 8 of the Consortium Agreement.
- In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the General Assembly, the Steering Committee shall advise the General Assembly on ways to rearrange tasks and budgets of the Parties concerned. Such rearrangement shall take into consideration any prior legitimate commitments which cannot be cancelled.

4.4. Advisory Board

NEMO will set up an Advisory Board including experts from target stakeholder groups. The Advisory Board (AB) will meet the Consortium at least once per year, joining every other General Assembly. When needed, further exchanges with the AB will be organized.

The AB is to provide the Consortium with guidance and sectorial insights to ensure the achievement of the project ambitions and to maximize the exploitation of results deriving from it, while supporting dissemination activities to maximize their reach and impact.

Prospective Advisory Board members are to be invited using the template official letter made available internally. Personal or centralized invitations are to be sent on a case-by-case basis upon discussion in the Steering Committee meetings. The scope of the contribution of the AB will be documented in the alignment of the SC agreement which would include the aspects of IP protection, degree of involvement, valorization of the results, etc. A non-disclosure alignment will be signed with all the Advisory Board members.

4.5. Meetings schedule

Table 1 summarizes the meetings envisioned in NEMO, including details of their planned frequency. Extraordinary meetings may be organized to adapt to project needs.

Table 1. Overview of planned meetings.

Meeting	Frequency	Organizer
Steering committee	1x/month	VUB
General Assembly	2x/year	Alternating beneficiaries: 1 st GA – TAAG 2 nd GA – ICONS 3 rd GA – VUB 4 th GA – IAV 5 th GA - TUG
Advisory Board + Consortium	1x/year (Every other GA)	Organizer of the corresponding GA
WP members*	1x/month	WP leader
Project coordination team	2x/month	VUB

** Meetings at WP level will cover task-related updates. When needed, bilateral meetings are to be organized.*

In addition to the meetings listed above, the Steering Committee will officially meet with CINEA in Review Meetings upon the end of the first (M18) and second (M36) reporting periods. Additional members of the Consortium are to join the Review Meetings upon invitation from the Steering Committee.

5. Quality assurance

5.1. Technical deliverables

The NEMO Consortium has agreed on an internal procedure to ensure the timely submission of high-quality deliverables. In the case of technical deliverables, it is as follows:

1. The deliverable leader uploads the report to the Cooperation Tool (CT5) with status ‘draft’ 2.5 weeks ahead of the submission deadline while informing VUB.
2. VUB circulates the draft via SharePoint to two WP leaders designated by the Steering Committee. The nominated reviewers have 1 week to review the draft, informing the deliverable leader and VUB upon the completion of their review.
3. The deliverable leader updates the draft considering the suggestions from the reviewers and forwards the final draft to VUB no later than 3 days before the submission deadline.
4. VUB makes a final check (inc. layout check when necessary) and submits the final version both in Sygma and in CT5.

	Responsible	Actions and timing	Status
1	Deliverable leader	2.5 weeks before deadline	Draft
		Draft version uploaded to CT5 notifying VUB, who coordinates the review process	
2	Reviewers	2.5 weeks before deadline (1-week review)	Under review
		Two WP leaders nominated by the Steering Committee review the draft and send their comments to VUB, who then liaises with the deliverable leader	
3	Deliverable leader	1.5 weeks before deadline	Revised draft
		Implementation of the comments from reviewers	
4	VUB	3 days before deadline	Final version
		Final check (inc. some final layout) and submission	

Figure 1. Overview of quality assurance procedure for technical deliverables.

5.2. Transversal deliverables

Transversal deliverables: Project Handbook, Data Management Plan, DEC Plan, Exploitation Plan, and their planned updates.

In the case of transversal deliverables, the procedure is as follows:

1. The deliverable leader uploads the report to CT5 with status ‘draft’ 2.5 weeks ahead of the submission deadline while informing VUB.
2. VUB circulates the draft to all partners via SharePoint. Project members have 1 week to add their feedback in a single shared file.

3. The deliverable leader updates the draft considering the suggestions from the project partners and forwards the final draft to VUB no later than 3 days before the submission deadline.
4. VUB makes a final check (inc. layout check when necessary) and submits the final version both in Sygma (i.e. EU Portal) and in CT5.

	Responsible	Actions and timing	Status
1	Deliverable leader	2.5 weeks before deadline	Draft
		Draft version uploaded to CT5 notifying VUB, who coordinates the review process	
2	Reviewers	2.5 weeks before deadline (1-week review)	Under review
		All partners review the draft and provide comments in a single shared file	
3	Deliverable leader	1.5 weeks before deadline	Revised draft
		Implementation of the comments from reviewers	
4	VUB	3 days before deadline	Final version
		Final check (inc. some final layout) and submission	

Figure 2. Overview of quality assurance procedure for transversal deliverables.

5.3. Milestones

The timely achievement of milestones is to be assessed by the SC. Both progress and technical completeness will be discussed in the SC monthly meetings, where two WP leaders may be nominated to review the related outputs. Where appropriate, the SC will propose mitigation actions in case of envisaged delays or additional needed technical activities to ensure its full achievement.

6. Risk Management

Risks are to be continually monitored by the Steering Committee with all the project partners being responsible for elevating unexpected developments to the corresponding WP leader and the Project Coordinator.

In its monthly meetings, the Steering Committee is to discuss about encountered challenges and to propose mitigation measures to be applied as soon as possible. When necessary, risks and/or measures are to be elevated to the General Assembly for voting. Task and WP leaders are responsible for the implementation of the agreed mitigation measures under the supervision of the Steering Committee.

All newly identified risks will be classified as for probability of occurrence and severity, and recorded in the NEMO risks log together with the related mitigation measures. The risks log, starting from that identified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, will be a living registry recorded both in CT5 and the project SharePoint to be updated when necessary.

7. Project management tool

7.1. Purpose

The Consortium will use the Cooperation Tool 5 (<https://cooperationtool5.eu/>) to ensure a smooth implementation of the project. CT5 will be the main internal project resource, being:

- An internal repository of all the documents produced during the project (see section 7.3 for reference).
- A centralized tool to record meetings at task, WP and project levels.
- A common platform for internal financial reporting and monitoring.

7.2. Access

All project members have been added as users in CT5. Changes in the team involved in the project (i.e. new members, leaving members, role changes, etc.) are to be communicated to the Coordinator to have an updated list of active members together with their responsibilities in the project.

Access rights are assigned to each Consortium member based on their roles at WP and project levels. The main access levels are as follows:

- Limited user: access to meetings and documents.
- User: access to and creation of documents, and access to meetings.
- Domain (WP) administrator: access to and creation of meetings and documents, manage rights within the domain (WP), change documents status, and create and manage action points derived from meetings.
- Project administrator: administration rights in all project domains.

Project members have access to resources with access level equal or lower to their assigned access level. Where necessary, access rights are tuned at WP level.

7.3. File management

All relevant documents (and their versions) produced in the project are to be uploaded to CT5. CT5 allows file versioning, thus enabling the unambiguous upload of intermediate and final versions.

Collaborative work on shared files should be done via the NEMO SharePoint, with relevant versions being recorded in CT5.

7.3.1. Document naming convention

Files uploaded to CT5 are assigned a unique document code consisting of 6 fields:

[Project] – [Domain] – [Type] – [Partner] – [Number] – [Version], where

- [Project] is NEMO
- [Domain] is the WP the document belongs in
- [Type] specifies the document category (see Table 2)
- [Partner] corresponds to the partner responsible for the document
- [Number] defines the document order in a given domain/WP
- [Version] represents the relevant iterations of the document

Table 2. Main document categories in CT5.

Category	[Type] code	Description
Administrative	A	General administrative documents (e.g. guidance documents)
Contractual	C	Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement
Deliverable	D	Deliverables as in the running version of the Grant Agreement
EC docs	E	Relevant documents from the EC (e.g. guidelines)
Meeting agenda, presentation or minutes	B	Meeting agenda, presentation or minutes
Periodic report	P	Final versions of periodic reports
Model (template)	M	General templates (deliverables, presentations, etc.) in Office formats
Technical contribution	T	Technical outputs that contribute to a given task but are not a deliverable per se

Example

The Grant Agreement is available in CT5 with the following document code:

NEMO – WP01 – C – VUB – 001 – 01

The Grant Agreement is a contractual document (**C**) which falls within WP1 (**WP01**) and the preparation of which was led by VUB (**VUB**). The Grant Agreement represents the first document in WP1 (**001**) and it's currently in its first version (**01**; an amended Grant Agreement would be version 02).

7.3.2. Document status

The four tags below are available in CT5 to flag the status of a certain document in its lifecycle.

- Draft: Document under development.
- Under review: Document being revised at task/WP/project level.
- Issued: Document in final and 'submission-ready' version.
- Obsolete: Document no longer relevant.

8. Financial Management

The Consortium has agreed to carry internal financial reports every 6 months via CT5 for financial monitoring. Financial administrators have been assigned the corresponding rights to use the Financial module in CT5; additional team members planning to use the financial reporting module should request the Coordinator to grant the needed rights. Beneficiary CSEM is not bound to the agreed procedure due to its Associated Partner nature and is to report directly to the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation, responsible for their national funding.

A meeting on financial management was held in June 2023 to introduce participants to the use of CT5 for financial management and to agree on operational aspects. The proposed procedures are as follows:

- Two reporting periods are envisaged in NEMO. Each reporting period covers three accounting periods (i.e. moments for internal financial reporting). An additional item will be created in the 2nd reporting period should any adjustments to the costs claimed in the 1st periodic report be needed.
- Participants can report estimated figures in accounting periods whenever real numbers are not yet available. The needed corrections to costs estimated in accounting periods can be applied at the end of reporting periods.
- Costs are to be reported at WP level in CT5.
- Participants are to internally record personnel costs using daily rates in line with Horizon Europe regulations. Despite the internal use of daily rates, effort is to be reported in person months in CT5.
- For simplicity, effort and personnel costs are to be reported aggregated per WP in the CT5 (i.e. reported effort/personnel costs correspond to the sum of effort/costs from all the staff from a participant having worked in a given WP during the time covered by the corresponding accounting period). Those participants willing to itemize effort/personnel costs by personnel category can do so by reporting the corresponding separate items.
- The end of accounting periods will be notified two weeks in advance, and partners will have two weeks to report in CT5 upon the end of the corresponding period.

E.g. For an accounting period ending on 30th November, a notice email would be sent on 15th November and the deadline to report in CT5 would be 15th December.

9. Repositories

9.1. Internal repository – CT5

The NEMO Consortium will use CT5 as the main internal repository, where all outputs produced during the project are to be made available to project participants. An overview of the main document categories is presented in section 7.3.

9.2. External repository – Zenodo

NEMO will be using a dedicated community in Zenodo as a public library of results derived from the project. All published content is to be linked to the Grant Agreement number to enable integration with the reporting line in Sygma.

The Consortium will aim at having as much content as possible available with 'open' access level. Where necessary, 'restricted' (i.e. access granted upon request), 'embargoed' and 'closed' access levels will be considered.

9.2.1. Target content

The community in Zenodo is aimed at increasing the findability, and thus visibility, of NEMO results and materials. Some proposed content to be uploaded to Zenodo is as follows:

- Public deliverables. In general once the deliverables have been approved. When relevant, the upload of public deliverables yet to be approved can be considered, but a note stating their preliminary (i.e. pending approval) status should be added.
- Open Access papers using the DOI provided by the publisher.
- Datasets
- Code
- Posters presented at conferences and papers in conference proceedings
- Etc.

9.2.2. Content curation

Project members that have produced relevant content should upload it to Zenodo. The direct upload link should be used for community disambiguation as there are multiple communities in Zenodo using the 'NEMO' acronym. The content uploaded to the community is to be approved to ensure that it only includes content linked to the project; VUB will act as gatekeeper by approving relevant uploads. Partners uploading content to Zenodo should notify VUB so the upload can be approved.

9.2.3. Considerations

When uploading a new item to Zenodo, basic information should be filled (e.g. title, authors, and description) while paying attention to some important fields. Some important aspects to be considered are as follows.

Communities. If using the direct upload link, the system will automatically detect the target community. Otherwise, make sure to type 'NEMO - Next generation models for advanced battery electronics' in the corresponding field.

A screenshot of the Zenodo 'Communities' selection interface. At the top, it says 'Communities' with a help icon and 'recommended' with a dropdown arrow. Below this is a text box with instructions: 'Specify communities which you wish your upload to appear in. The owner of the community will be notified, and can either accept or reject your request. Please make sure your record complies with the content policy of the communities you add; reported abuse will be followed by account inactivation.' Below the instructions is a search bar containing the text 'NEMO - Next generation models for advanced battery electronics'. A search icon is on the right of the search bar. Below the search bar is a blue highlighted result box with the text: 'NEMO - Next generation models for advanced battery electronics' and 'The NEMO project "Next generation models for advanced battery electronics" has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation p...'

Digital object identifier (DOI). If the content to be uploaded already has a DOI assigned (i.e. paper published in Open Access), make sure to specify it to avoid redundancy. Otherwise, the field can be left empty and Zenodo will assign a newly generated DOI.

License. Zenodo supports over 400 licenses. Project members can refer to a license wizard to select the most appropriate option upon consultation with their Data Management and/or Tech Transfer unit(s).

Funding. Make sure to specify the Grant Agreement number so the content can be linked to the project.

Related/alternate identifiers. If the content being uploaded is linked to other items that already have identifiers, these can be specified here.

E.g.: When uploading a dataset linked to an article already published, the DOI of the paper can be added in this field.

10. Internal and external communication strategy

10.1. Plan for dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PDEC)

The PDEC (D8.1, M6) will outline a holistic Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy aimed at producing significant and long-term impacts among the NEMO's target audiences on the battery value chain.

The Plan will be regularly updated along the project lifetime, optimizing the measures described to ensure the highest effectiveness and incorporate insights and data collected from a regular monitoring activity, conducted through the application of quantitative metrics and dedicated performance Indexes¹ (developed in-house by ICONS).

The identification of key exploitable results and a stakeholder mapping exercise will be integrated in the second update of the Plan (D8.2, M18) and form a solid baseline upon which the final strategy will be developed and executed.

10.2. Communication strategy

The communication strategy will build an effective framework for public outreach and engagement with civil society at large, to spread the project goals and results with accessible messages and tools. Specifically, the strategy aims at spreading awareness and understanding about innovative battery management systems and transport and stationary applications, unveiling how they could play a critical role towards more sustainable, efficient and safe battery operations, reducing environmental and economic costs.

The identification of key stakeholders and understanding of their needs and priorities is crucial to allow effective dissemination. This will make NEMO's results available to the scientific community, policymakers, and industry, with the ultimate scope to facilitate scientific advancement, community building, and evidence-based policy making.

10.3. Internal communication procedures

The project will have clearly defined internal communication procedures. While the below is relevant to the project from the start, further information will be available in the PDEC (D8.1, M6).

10.3.1. Editorial content

As WP8 leader, ICONS assumes the primary responsibility for producing DC formats and ensures the quality of all content published on the NEMO platforms. This includes being the

chief editor and having the final approval authority for all productions, ensuring that visuals adhere to the brand book and that key messages effectively convey the project's personality.

The Project Coordinator and the Steering Committee will provide input and feedback throughout production to guarantee scientific accuracy of the content. Moreover, the Steering Committee is consulted any time the dissemination level of technical and scientific information needs to be assessed (cases detailed in Table 3).

When prompted by ICONS, partners can provide other input and feedback (i.e., texts, suggest use of pictures, footage). For each organization, a contact point for D&C is identified and is consulted to provide feedback on certain products and contents. ICONS will have the final call as to whether to incorporate such input. In any case, edits cannot be implemented once the final product is ready.

10.3.2. Publications and events template

Partners will keep track of the upcoming publications and events. They will inform the rest of the Consortium about their publications and/or their wish to participate on behalf of NEMO. Publications and events attendance will be monitored through a regular communication flow happening within the consortium and updates will be collected on a six-month basis through a dedicated template.

10.3.3. Stakeholders database

The creation of a database originates from the stakeholder mapping described in the PDEC. This database will gain significance in the second year of the project when noteworthy results are produced. Throughout the project, the database will be updated as needed. Once the Stakeholders database is populated, partners will be requested to identify stakeholder organizations they are in contact with.

10.3.4. Consortium communication

Internal communication will be favored via a series of recurring meetings at task, WP and project levels (Table 1), with additional meetings to be organized when necessary. Online meetings are to be hosted via Teams or similar platforms such as Webex. Where appropriate, partners are to consider the use of discussion forums available in CT5.

An updated contacts list is available in the NEMO SharePoint and represents the basis for the members database in CT5, which allows to retrieve distribution lists by project role. Partners are to timely communicate any workforce-related changes to ensure having an up-to-date members database.

Project members are advised to use a common email subject structure for clarity:

NEMO – WPX Target topic

10.4. External communication procedures

In line with art. 17 of the Grant Agreement, beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences. Thus, external communication must be pursued by all partners.

As already stated in this document, ICONS is leader of editorial content and ensures the quality of all content published on the NEMO platforms. For all external communication about NEMO, partners will follow NEMO communications guidelines, with reference to the brand book and the PDEC.

All partners are required to observe the dissemination level of documents and deliverables (PU – Public/SEN – Sensitive). When uploading documents in CT5, partners must make sure that the document is clearly labeled.

In the case of stakeholder relations, partners nominating the organizations in the stakeholder database will assume the responsibility of directly engaging and liaising with them to disseminate project results.

Key messages for communication with critical stakeholders will be developed in the context of the PDEC, in collaboration with the Steering Committee members.

ICONS manages and maintains external communication channels, ensuring the quality of all content published on the NEMO platforms. To ensure quality and protection of confidential information, the Consortium will follow the procedure detailed in the table below.

Table 3. NEMO procedure for the publication of editorial content.

Content	Procedure
Press and news release and project updates	Produced and approved by ICONS. When prompted, partners can provide input and feedback.
Journalistic articles	Steering Committee is involved in the initial stage (i.e., to define the topic). The article is produced by a professional journalist and approved by ICONS.
Video	Produced and approved by ICONS. When prompted, partners can provide input and feedback on the script of the video.
Leaflet	Produced and approved by ICONS. When prompted, partners can provide input and feedback on the text of the leaflet.
Info-packs, factsheets, final booklet, policy brief	Produced by ICONS with partners' contribution. Final approval by Steering Committee is requested.

Further information on external communication procedures will be available in the PDEC (D8.1, M6).

11. Deviations

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

12. References

[1] Folco Giuliana, Gaboardi Elena, Lischetti Serena, Martinoli Mario, Mazzolo Giulio, & Schmid Elisabeth (2022). Two new tools for science communication assessment: the community engagement index and communication effectiveness quadrants. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6985584>